

Analysis plan: Layered analysis of fMRI data
acquired during attention to heart

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1 Introduction

This document contains the analysis plan for the LAYMM-Heart study. It was written after MRI data acquisition and image reconstruction was finished. This analysis plan describes the layered analysis of an fMRI study using the previously established "heartbeat attention" paradigm (Petzschner et al. 2019). It closely follows the analysis plan of the LAYMM-aMMN study, a dataset which was acquired with the same participants, but with an auditory MMN paradigm. An initial whole brain analysis for identifying Region of interests (ROIs) was performed on smoothed data, according to a separate pre-registered analysis (https://gitlab.ethz.ch/tnu/analysis-plans/muellerschraderetal_hbatt_ohbm) and presented at OHBM 2023.

1.1 Motivation

The goal of this study is to investigate modulatory effects of attention to one's own heartbeat on (layered) neuronal activity in the insula.

In current theories of perception, attention plays important role in modulating the relative importance of exteroceptive (perception of states of the external world) stimuli (Lindsay 2020). However, its role in interoception (perception of bodily states) is far less established.

Here, we use a heartbeat attention task (Petzschner et al. 2019) to compare attention to an interoceptive stimulus (one's own heartbeat) against attention to an exteroceptive stimulus (auditory white noise) within the insula, a key cortical region for interoception (Craig 2003).

The acquired functional MRI data with sub-millimeter resolution allows us to not only conduct *conventional* functional analyses but also to investigate laminar differences of activation.

In a first step, we aim to localize those regions of the insula which show activation when attending to heartbeats. This was presented on a subset of the participants at OHBM, according to the initial analysis plan (see above).

In a second step, we plan to examine the layered distribution of the observed attentional effects in the insula. Specifically, our main research question is whether there exists an interaction between laminar depth (upper versus lower layers) and the target of attention (towards heartbeats versus auditory stimuli) and if so, which forms this interaction takes.

2 Paradigm and data acquisition

2.1 Heartbeat attention paradigm and stimulus presentation

The paradigm employed in this study is the same as in Petzschner et al. 2019, but brain activity was measured with fMRI instead of EEG: 40 participants were measured with functional MRI at 7 Tesla while listening to

white noise played to them through earphones. The paradigm consisted of 4 runs with 16 blocks per run (block duration 20s). In each block, participants were instructed to either focus on their heartbeat (*interoceptive condition*) or the white noise sound (*exteroceptive condition*). To foster the participants' engagement in the task, they had to answer control questions after each block. Dependent on the block type (attention to heart/sound) these questions referred to their perception of their heartbeat/the auditory white noise.

2.2 MR data acquisition

Participants were scanned on a Philips Achieva 7 Tesla MRI system (Philips Healthcare, Best, The Netherlands) using a quadrature transmit and 32-channel head receive array (Nova Medical, Wilmington, MA).

Functional images were acquired using a high-resolution single-shot spiral-out trajectory with 0.9 mm in-plane resolution (parallel acceleration $R = 4$, $T_E = 15$ ms, 50 ms readout duration), combined in a multi-slice 2D sequence with 36 slices (0.9 mm/ 0.1 mm slice thickness/gap) and fat suppression module (SPIR), amounting to a volume TR of 3.128 seconds (similar to Kasper et al. 2022, but with a different resolution). For each participant, we recorded four fMRI runs with 180 volumes each. Between runs 1 and 2, between runs 3 and 4 and after run 4, a fat-suppressed 2D Cartesian gradient-echo scan ($R = 1$) with six echos, 1 mm in-plane resolution and a slice geometry equivalent to the functional images, was acquired (to calculate B_0 map and SENSE map). Furthermore, a structural T_1 image with 0.8 mm isotropic resolution (Inversion recovery 3D Cartesian gradient-echo) and another 1 mm multi-echo Cartesian scan ($R=3$) with whole brain coverage (120 slices) was measured for anatomical reference.

2.3 Physiological and additional data

During scanning, heart rate was recorded using both a pulse oximeter and ECG, and breathing with a breathing belt. Since the ECG data was too noisy for a reliable detection of peaks, we will only use the data from the pulse oximeter and the breathing belt for the physiological noise correction (see subsection 5.2).

2.4 Quality control: Incomplete data

We will exclude subjects, for whom we do not have the full (functional) raw data for all four runs. In case of missing data for the reconstruction of the Multi-Echo (ME) images, we will exclude the participant, if we do not have

complete data for at least one run to reconstruct.¹ Furthermore, we will exclude a participant if we do not have any T_1 image (neither from HEART nor from the auditory MMN-session).

In case of missing stimulation data (exact timing of onsets and offsets), we will replace that information by the nominal on- and offsets.² For subjects with incomplete physiological data, see subsection 5.2.

3 Reconstruction of MRI images

The reconstruction of images based on spiral trajectories requires the usage and inversion of an advanced signal model which takes - besides the sensitivity encoding of the coils (SENSE maps) - separately measured spatial (B_0 maps) and dynamic imperfections (concomitant fields) into account (Kasper et al. 2022).³ MR images are reconstructed on a local ETH cluster using an in-house implementation of the reconstruction algorithm described there.

Using the advanced signal model, the quality of the reconstructed (f)MRI images depends of course also on the quality of the auxiliary data (SENSE maps, B_0 maps, concomitant fields) and their processing. For completeness, we include the reconstruction procedure in this analysis plan.

3.1 Reconstruction of fMRI (and ME) images

Image reconstruction follows the same strategy as in Kasper et al. 2022. Here, we will recapitulate some aspects which are important for the quality control procedure:

Shortly, ME images are reconstructed and B_0 maps and SENSE maps are computed from them. These form - together with the concomitant fields - the auxiliary data for the reconstruction. Image reconstruction is specifically sensitive to the B_0 maps.⁴

Misestimation of the B_0 map results in blurring, ripple artifacts or even signal dropouts in the reconstructed functional images and can hence be easily detected by visual inspection.

There are some steps in the computation and processing of the B_0 maps, where small variations in the algorithms can have a strong influence on the quality of the reconstructed images (details on masking of ME images, unwrapping, extrapolation, smoothing). We will exploit these degrees of

¹Note that in that case, we still might exclude the participant after reconstruction due to the bad quality of the B_0 map.

²An analysis over complete datasets showed that the difference between nominal and actual onsets and offsets is typically in the range of 0.1 s to 0.2 s, which is low compared to the block length of 20 s.

³Note that ME and fMRI images are reconstructed offline, while the T_1 images are reconstructed directly by the scanner software.

⁴This is due to the high field strength of 7 T, the spiral readout (and the resulting shape of the PSF) and the high resolution (and the resulting long readout duration).

freedom to improve the quality of the reconstructed images until we obtain an acceptable quality based on visual inspection (see subsection 3.2). This decision (acceptable quality, further improvements necessary or exclusion of the subject) will be done purely based on the visual inspection and before any of the further analyses will be done.

3.2 Quality control of reconstructed images

We will exclude subjects if the (visual) quality of the reconstructed images is not sufficient and cannot be improved by altering e.g. the computation of B_0 maps.

Visual indications of non-sufficient image quality are (with possible cause):

- Strong blurring (B_0 map)
- Strong *ripple* artifacts (B_0 map)
- Signal dropouts (B_0 map)
- *SENSE* artifacts (SENSE map)

In case of local artifacts probably related to misestimation of the B_0 map, e.g. close to air-tissue boundaries, we will not exclude the participant, if the insula is not (or in the case of the ventral-anterior insula not strongly) affected by that artifact.

The judgement on the visual quality will be performed based on the first and the last image of each run. If during preprocessing (see subsection 4.2) realignment parameters indicate phases of strong absolute displacement (≥ 2 mm), the visual quality will also be assessed also for these volumes (see also 4.3).⁵

4 Preprocessing (functional data)

MR images will be processed using SPM12 (v. 7219).

4.1 Preparation of multi-echo images

For each subject, we will average the whole-brain ME image (RMS over echos) and perform unified segmentation (Ashburner and Friston 2005/`spm_segment`) on the result.

The resulting bias-corrected average image `mrmsmewb.nii` will serve as anatomical reference towards which all other images will be aligned, coregistered etc. The obtained transformation `y.nii` will hence serve as reference mapping between the subject space (defined by `mrmsmewb.nii`) and the MNI space.

⁵This is done since the B_0 map might not be accurate for strong displacements.

We will create a mask of the insula in subject space (`mask_mrsmewb.nii`) by applying the inverse normalization `i_y.nii` to the original (MNI space) mask of the insula (c.f. section 6).

4.2 Preprocessing of functional images

In order to account for T_1 -saturation effects, the first 4 images of each run will be discarded.

First all four runs will be slice-timing corrected and then re-aligned in a two-pass-strategy:

1. First with respect to the first image
2. Then with respect to the mean image of the first realignment
3. After realignment, all images will be resliced to the grid defined by the first volume.
4. The mean functional image will then be segmented and bias field corrected using unified segmentation
5. The bias-field-corrected mean image will be coregistered (rigid body transformation) to the multi-echo image (`mrsmewb.nii`).
6. All functional images will be transformed in the same way (but not resliced!).

All further processing will be done on the images resliced in step 3 (in order to keep the original resolution), but reoriented to match the reference multi-echo image.

In order to take into account abrupt motion by participants, we will compute Framewise Displacement (FD) and include a confound regressor that represents each volume with a $FD \geq 0.5mm$, i.e. where the motion is larger than half of our voxel size.

Furthermore, to compensate for blurring in the reconstruction due to the mismatch of the B_0 map, we will include additional confound regressors for each volume with a total translational displacement⁶ of more than 3 mm with respect to the first or last image⁷ - dependent on whether the ME image to compute the B_0 map has been acquired before or after the functional block.

4.3 Quality control of preprocessed data

We will exclude participants, if they have one or more runs with more than 36 additional confound regressors (due to FD or absolute displacement).

⁶Measured in the usual Euclidean distance.

⁷During quality control of subsection 3.2, we look at all images with a total displacement of at least 2 mm. If we already observe blurring problems for displacements of 2 mm to 3 mm, we will adapt this threshold accordingly.

5 Physiological noise correction

5.1 Preparation of nuisance regressors (PhysIO)

We will use the PhysIO Toolbox R 2022b, V,8.2.0 to create fMRI nuisance regressors based on pulse oximeter and breathing belt measurements. We will follow the procedure described in Kasper et al. 2017 to create

- RETROICOR regressors (Glover, Li, and Ress 2000) of cardiac (3rd order) and respiratory phase (2th order / + 1st order interaction)
- a respiratory volume per time regressor (RVT /Birn et al. 2008)
- a heart rate regressor (to take into account effects due to heart rate variability (HRV), see Chang, Cunningham, and Glover 2009 for details).

This will result in 16 physiological regressors that will be combined with the 6 motion traces estimated during realignment to serve as confound regressors in the GLM.

5.2 Quality control for physiological noise regressors

Using the visualization functionality of the PhysIO toolbox, we will inspect the detection of heart beats and inhalation and respiration and correct them manually, if they occur too often (≥ 10 times per block).

In case of partially missing physiological data, we will still compute the above regressors as long as at least half of the run duration is covered.

6 Anatomical insula mask

6.1 In MNI space

We will use the Human Brainnetome Atlas (Fan et al. 2016) to define an anatomical mask of the insula in MNI space (Region numbers 163 - 174).

In particular, we will use its six subdivision of the insula into

- Hypergranular insula (G)
- Ventral agranular insula (vIa)
- Dorsal agranular insula (dLa)
- Ventral dysgranular and granular insula (vId/vIg)
- Dorsal granular insula (dIg)
- Dorsal dysgranular insula (dId)

to define the regions of interest.

6.2 In (functional) subject space

When transforming the categorical masks (with the insular subdivisions like *left hypergranular insula*, *right hypergranular insula*,... as categories), we will first transform the individual (0-1) masks for each category (for example *left hypergranular insula*) to the new geometry and threshold the floating values (coming from the interpolation) at a level of > 0.5 . To account for normalization uncertainty, we will inflate each mask by 2 voxel after transforming it to the geometry of the MEs. If, after this inflation, a voxel is contained in more than one mask, we will consult the unthresholded masks in subject geometry (see above) and assign the voxel to the category with the highest value in the unthresholded mask.

7 Processing of anatomical images and reconstruction of surfaces

7.1 Preprocessing of T1 images (SPM)

The T_1 -weighted image will be segmented and bias corrected by unified segmentation (Ashburner and Friston 2005) and coregistered by rigid body transformation to the multi-echo `mrmsmewb.nii`.⁸

7.2 Reconstruction of grey matter surfaces

We will use Freesurfer (v. 7.4.0-1 / Fischl 2012) to reconstruct cortical Grey Matter (GM) surfaces (GM/White Matter (WM) and GM/pial surface).

We start with the automated structural MRI processing stream (Freesurfer's `recon_all` command), which performs an automated GM/WM segmentation and creates GM surfaces. This will be done based on the T_1 -weighted image (in its native resolution).

We will inspect the results, perform *persistent edits* (see *Edits - Free Surfer Wiki* 2023) on places with problems in the segmentation/creation of surfaces and rerun the analyses. This will be repeated if further edits are required to visually match surfaces and the corresponding T_1 -weighted image.

Note that the *persistent edits* will be stored in separate files, which we will keep, so that the manual interventions will be always documented and we can reproduce the analysis.

⁸Note that we do not reslice the T_1 image, but only keep the information regarding the transformation in the header).

7.2.1 Persistent edits

We will perform the persistent edits in order to correct for errors in segmentation, resulting in wrong surfaces. To diagnose these errors, we will use both, T_1 -weighted image and ME images. If the contrasts of the two images lead to different conclusions, we will - since we expect more problems with the contrast of the T_1 -weighted image (compare subsection 7.5)- rely on the contrast of the ME images. In case of geometric incongruence between T_1 -weighted image and ME image, we will - since it is primarily used - rely on the T_1 -weighted image.

7.3 Creation of upper and lower laminar surfaces

Using Freesurfer's `mrismooth`, we will smooth the GM surfaces (with 1 iteration and 0 averages). We will then perform volumetric layering (see Waehnert et al. 2014) to create surfaces at 25% and 75% cortical depth with surface tools (Wagstyl and Huth 2023). These surfaces will serve as a reference for infra- and supragranular layers, respectively.

7.4 Creation of laminar masks

We will create laminar masks in functional subject space by including all voxel whose distance of the center from the infra- respective supragranular surfaces is ≤ 0.5 mm.

Voxels that are assigned to both the infra- and supragranular layer will be excluded from further analysis.⁹

7.5 Quality control

We will manually check the registration between the T_1 -weighted image and the Whole-Brain Multi-Echo (MEWB) before performing the reconstruction of surfaces.

For the visual quality control of the surface estimation, compare subsection 7.2.1.

After the measurements were finished, quality assurance had revealed a reduced WM/GM contrast in the right hemisphere of the T_1 -weighted images. This contrast reduction was caused by an inhomogeneous excitation pattern of the excitation pulse and consequently partly incomplete inversion of the magnetization in the inversion recovery scan. This reduced contrast renders the automatic segmentation of Freesurfer more challenging and might cause an increased need for manual interventions in the right hemisphere. In case this becomes too complicated, we will decide to use only data from the left hemisphere.

⁹Note that this is very unlikely for a cortical thickness > 2 mm, like in the insula (see Tanzer et al. 2021)

We will overlay the final (smoothed) GM surfaces on the mean bias-corrected functional image from subsection 4.2 and check if they coincide for the insula. In case of small systematic shifts (indicating improper rigid-body alignment during coregistration), we will shift the surfaces accordingly and include the corresponding transformation as a hard-coded step in the analysis pipeline.

In the lower slices of the fMRI images (ventral anterior insula), we might observe geometric distortions due to the misestimation of the B_0 map. If we have indications for that (differences between surfaces and contrast-changes in the images), we will exclude this subregion of the respective subject from the analysis.

8 Main research question

Our main research question is whether there exists an interaction between laminar depth (upper versus lower layers) and the target of attention (towards heartbeats versus auditory stimuli) and if so, which forms this interaction takes. In order to address this question, in a first step, we need to create functional masks consisting of voxels that show a differential response for attention to the heartbeat versus sounds. These functional masks will then be combined with anatomical masks of different insular regions and of infragranular/supragranular layers. Our research question will be investigated for each insular region separately while correcting for multiple testing.

9 Creation of functional masks

For each subject, we will compute an individual functional mask in the subject space.

9.1 First-level GLM

For the first level analysis, we will create a GLM consisting of

- a regressor *attention to heart* (blocked),
- a regressor *attention to sound* (blocked),
- the following nuisance regressors
 - 18 *physiological* regressors (see subsection 5.1)
 - 6 *motion* regressors (see subsection 5.1)
 - *stick* regressors for volumes with extreme movement (either FD of > 0.5 mm or absolute displacement of > 3 mm/ see subsection 4.2)

We are then interested in the contrast

$$c_1 = \textit{attention to heart} - \textit{attention to sound}. \quad (1)$$

9.2 Functional masking

We will compute the subject-individual functional mask based on the F -contrast c_1 (see Equation 1) on functional data smoothed with a Gaussian kernel with a FWHM of 3 mm, thresholded at $p < 0.001$ (uncorrected).

10 Creation of layered functional maps

For each subregion of the insula, we will create layered functional maps by applying the following mask on the functional data:

First we take a logical AND of

- the anatomical mask of the insular subregion (section 6)
- the layered mask for infragranular/supragranular layers (subsection 7.4)
- the functional mask (subsection 9.2).

In a second step, we will ensure that the masks contain the same part of cortex on each layer:

- For each voxel in the, say, lower layer, we will compute the closest node in the corresponding (lower) surface (see subsection 7.3)
- For that node in the lower surface, we have a corresponding node in the upper surface
- For that node in the upper surface, we will look for its neighbouring nodes (connected by an edge).
- If no voxel in the upper surface has any of these neighbouring nodes as nearest neighbour, we will exclude the original voxel (in the lower layer). Otherwise we will keep it.

We repeat the step for all voxels in the upper layer.

Please note that, in this first analysis, we do not include a mask of the pial veins, which could be considered to limit the effect of draining veins. This could be an option in the future.

11 Second level analysis

For each subregion, we will perform the following analysis. For each surface (25%/75% cortical depth), we will compute a weighted $\beta_{\text{att to heart/sound}}$ average over voxel. This is done to account for partial volume effects. Each voxel v is hereby weighted by a weight depending on its distance to the corresponding surface:

$$w_v = \max(0, 1 - 2 \cdot d(S, v)). \quad (2)$$

Here $d(S, v)$ denotes the distance between the voxel center and the corresponding surface (in mm). Hence, voxels which are centered on the surfaces S , have full weight 1 and the weight reduces the further the voxel center is away from the surface. Voxels more than 0.5 mm away from the surface have weight 0 and are thus not taken into account.

We will then analyse the averaged β s in a 2-way ANOVA (upper vs. lower surface/ attention to heart vs. attention to sound) and test the interaction term with an F -test against a null hypothesis of no effect. Note that the interaction is orthogonal to the effect of attention, which served as a contrast to define the functional ROI.

To correct for multiple comparison (12 tests: 6 ROIs per hemisphere x 2 hemispheres), we will apply a Bonferroni-Holm correction to control the family-wise error rate below $p < 0.05$.

For those regions that show a significant interaction in the above F -test, in order to understand its nature, we will visualise the interaction and compute layer-specific effect sizes (Cohen's d) for contrast c_1 .

12 Layered profiles

To visualize the signal differences across cortical depth, we will compute average values across cortical depth for $\beta_{\text{attention to heart}}$ and $\beta_{\text{attention to sound}}$, respectively for each ROI (averaged over subjects and runs).

For each ROI and condition, we will compute a histogram with bins centered at a relative depth of

$$5\%, 15\%, \dots, 85\%, 95\%$$

by - following the equi-volume-principle - creating surfaces at cortical depth of

$$0\%, 10\%, \dots, 90\%, 100\%$$

and averaging the β s for all voxel whose center lies between the two surfaces. For example, for the 15% bin, we will average all β , whose voxel center lies between the 10% and the 20% surface.

13 Out-of-sample prediction

If clear differences are observable in the laminar profiles from section 12, we will perform the following post-hoc-analysis:

In order to show that there is a systematic difference between the layered profiles in the different conditions (*attention to sound* vs. *attention to heart*), we will use out-of-sample prediction to predict the condition based on the (normalized) layered profile.

For each subject, ROI and run, we will calculate the layered profiles as described in section 12. To compensate for global signal differences, we will normalize the profile/histograms by a z -transformation.

We will then train a binary classifier (based on Support Vector Machines (SVMs)) on the condition and test it using leave-one-subject-out cross validation:

For each subject¹⁰, we will train the classifier on the remaining other subjects, and test it then on the 4 runs \times 2 conditions. For each region, we will report the accuracy averaged over subjects.

¹⁰If we excluded certain runs of a subject during quality control, we will not use that subject for this analysis.

A References

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B Glossary

B_0 map Spatial offresonance map. Calculated from Multi-Echo images. 5–8, 12

SENSE map Coil SENSitivity Encoding map. Calculated from Multi-Echo images. 5–7

C Abbreviations

ANOVA Analysis of Variance 14

ECG Electrocardiography 5

EEG Electroencephalography 4

FD Framewise Displacement 8, 12

fMRI functional Magnetic Resonant Imaging 4–6, 9, 12

FWHM Full Width at Half-Maximum 13

GLM General Linear Model 12

GM Grey Matter 10–12

ME Multi-Echo 5–8, 10, 11

MEWB Whole-Brain Multi-Echo 11

MMN Mismatch Negativity 4, 6

MNI Montréal Institute of Neurology 7–9

MR Magnetic Resonance 6, 7

MRI Magnetic Resonant Imaging 4, 5

PSF Point Spread Function 6

RMS Root Mean Square 7

ROI Region of interest 4, 14, 15

SVM Support Vector Machine 15

WM White Matter 10, 11